

Nest building materials for sows during farrowing - Short review

Lene Juul Pedersen, Anita Hoofs, Antje Schubbert

info.pigs@eurcaw.eu

www.eurcaw-pigs.eu

Nest building materials for sows during farrowing – Short review

Lene Juul Pedersen¹, Anita Hoofs², Antje Schubbert³

¹ Aarhus University, Denmark

² Wageningen Livestock Research, The Netherlands

³ Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Germany

May 2024

This short review is a publication of the European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare Pigs (EURCAW-Pigs). EURCAW-Pigs was designated by the European Union on 5 March 2018 through Regulation (EU) 2018/329, in accordance with Articles 95 and 96 of Regulation (EU) 2017/625.

Colophon and disclaimer

Access to document at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12679800>. Also to be downloaded at <https://edepot.wur.nl/661808>

This review gives an overview of the motivation behind nest building behaviour and its behavioural elements. The review also describes how lack of ability to nest build influences maternal behaviour and sow and piglet welfare. Finally, it describes which materials can be provided for nest building when sows are kept confined in crates or zero confinement systems.

EURCAW-Pigs organised an internal review prior to publication of the final document. However, it cannot accept liability for any damage resulting from the use of the results of this study or the application of the advice contained in it.

info.pigs@eurcaw.eu

www.eurcaw-pigs.eu

Contents

1	Summary	3
2	Background.....	3
3	Nest building behaviour in semi-natural conditions	3
4	Nest building under production conditions	4
	4.1 Farrowing crates or temporary crating	4
	4.2 Zero confinement.....	5
5	Conclusions	6
	<i>Acknowledgement</i>	6
6	References.....	7

1 Summary

This review gives an overview of the motivation behind nest building behaviour and its behavioural elements. The review also describes how lack of ability to nest build influences maternal behaviour and sow and piglet welfare. Finally, it describes which materials can be provided for nest building when sows are kept confined in crates or zero confinement systems, and to what extent they meet the need for nest building. The knowledge compiled in this short review relates to the EURCAW-Pigs reviews [Farrowing housing and management](#) and [Alternatives to farrowing crates](#) (Pedersen et al., 2020 & 2023, respectively).

2 Background

The Council Directive 2008/120/EC (Council of the European Union 2008) states in Annex I, Chapter II B that: “In the week before the expected farrowing time sows and gilts must be given suitable nesting material in sufficient quantity, unless it is not technically feasible for the slurry system used in the establishment”.

Nest building is covered by the welfare directive since nest building is a strong behavioural need driven by hormones. Preventing nesting behaviour, e.g. by lack of space and/or lack of nest materials, is as such associated with frustration and stress, and therefore associated with poor welfare. The onset of nest building is triggered by changes in hormones prior to birth, e.g. prolactin. The termination of nest building is regulated by a combination of changes in hormones (increasing levels of oxytocin) and by features of the constructed nest (reviewed by Algers et al., 2007).

3 Nest building behaviour in semi-natural conditions

In semi-natural environment the sow leaves the social group 1-2 days prior to farrowing and walks up to 5-6 km to find a suitable nest site (Jensen, 1986). Depending on the season, nests-sites are often positioned away from the social group and in a protected area, e.g. under trees and with a clear view over the surrounding (Mayer et al., 2002; Jensen, 1989; Stolba and Wood-Gush, 1989). Various materials such as branches, stems, leaves, pine-needles, mosses, hay and straw are used for nest building (Mayer et al., 2022). The nest building consists of several phases: selection of a nest site, digging a shallow hole and gathering and arranging suitable materials into a form. Finally, the sow will lay down in the nest a few hours before birth of first piglet(s) (reviewed by Swan et al., 2023).

The behavioural elements and the strength and duration of the various behaviours depend on the nest materials available, the appearance of the nest site and the climate. For example, sows gather less materials if the nest site is situated e.g. in front of a hill where the nest gets some protection from the surrounding. Also, it has been shown that sows gather more materials during cold than hot seasons (Jensen, 1989).

The expression of the various phases of nesting behaviour as well as features of the constructed nest, affect the nesting activity (Jensen, 1993). For example, Damm et al. (2000), showed that when sows had access to more complex materials they express more intense nesting behaviour, while they terminated nest building earlier compared to time of farrowing. Thus, likely the performance of the nesting activities themselves appears to play a significant role in reducing the motivation, and so does the visual appearance of the

constructed nest (Arey et al., 1991). The last hours before and during farrowing the sow lies still in lateral position with the udder exposed, except for getting up to nose/sniff the first piglet(s) born (Jensen, 1989; Stolba and Wood-Gush, 1989).

In the piglet's first 4-7 days of life, the sow stays close to the nest (nest bound phase). During this period, the sow only leaves the nest occasionally for foraging and drinking and for defecation and urination. At the end of the nest bound phase, the sow returns to the social group and piglets will follow (Stolba and Wood-Gush, 1989; Jensen, 1989).

After farrowing, the isolation and the nest itself support piglet survival in several ways. When sows seek isolation during farrowing and the first days after, the risk of piglets being crushed by other adults is reduced/eliminated. In addition, isolation from other sows and their offspring, hinder older piglets to compete with the new-born for access to the colostrum and sow milk. By isolation herself from the remaining group, the farrowing sows ensures that her resources (milk) benefit only her own offspring in order to support their survival and growth. The nest itself thermally protects the piglets by drying up the birth fluid and by increasing the temperature considerably around the sow's udder (Algers and Jensen 1990). Thus, the constructed nest plays an important role for piglet survival by several means.

However, not only the nest as such supports piglet survival and growth. So does the expression of the nesting behaviour itself. Research have shown that more intense nest building behaviour with high quality nest materials reduce the activity during parturition, increase the sow's attention towards her piglets when lying down, reduce near-crushing events, stimulate hormones involved in milk let down and increase piglet growth and survival (Yun et al., 2013, 2014, 2015; Pedersen et al. 2003; Bolhuis et al. 2018; Westin et al. 2014, 2015; Andersen et al. 2005; Vestergaard and Hansen, 1984).

4 Nest building under production conditions

Under production conditions, sows are still highly motivated to seek out an isolated nest site for nest building. Therefore, it is important that the farrowing environment provide both sufficient space, as well as sufficient amount and quality of nest materials (Thodberg et al. 1999; Roswold et al. 2018).

4.1 Farrowing crates or temporary crating

Sows in farrowing crates cannot isolate themselves and they have limited possibility to express most of the complex nesting behaviours. Therefore, signs of stress and frustration are more evident in crated sows during the peri-partum period than in sows kept loose (Lawrence et al. 1994; Damm et al. 2003a; Oliverio et al. 2008). Indicators of hindered nest building performance are high level of re-directed nest building behaviour towards bars and pen equipment (Yun et al., 2015), stereotypic like behaviours and/or low intensity and quality of the nesting behaviours (Damm et al., 2003a; Thodberg et al., 1999), and nesting behaviour or restlessness close to start of farrowing (Westin et al., 2005).

Allocation of nest materials to crated sows is limited by the fact that materials as straw, hay, wood shaving and similar, quickly (few minutes) get out of reach of the sows. In addition, many farrowing crates have fully slatted or drained floors which further limit the allocation of nest materials without adding the risk of blocking the slats and/or slurry system. Despite these limitations, several studies do indicate that allocation of nest

materials to crated sows to some extent reduce signs of stress and frustration. For example, compared to no materials, straw in a rack or jute/hessian materials attached to the front of the pen decreased stress hormones and reduced re-directed behaviours during the nest building phase (Markland et al., 2023; Plush et al., 2021). Similarly, provision of saw dust increased nesting activities when small amount of saw dust (a hand full) was provided every 30-60 min during the day of nesting (Cronin et al., 1993). Swan et al. (2018) showed more nestbuilding and less bar biting (a redirected nest building behaviour) when newspapers were provided compared to straw and wood shavings. Swan et al. (2018) allocated the materials in front of the sow on a slatted floor three times daily in an amount equal to 2-3 l in volume per provision. Authors reported that sows ate part of the straw and that the slatted floor caused the materials to disappear rather quickly.

Figure 4.1.1: When sows are crated during nest building, loose materials do not work well since they get out of reach of the sow (©WUR).

4.2 Zero confinement

The extent to which sows in zero confinement systems can nest build and construct a functional nest still largely depends on space, floor type and pen design as well as quality and quantity of the materials provided.

As for crated sows, loose sows are mostly kept in individual farrowing pens in a large room with multiple pens next to each others. Thus, sows have no possibility to select an isolated nest site away from neighbouring sows. However, pen design can partly accommodate for some kind of isolation to neighbouring sows by setting up solid walls in part of pen (Pedersen et al. 2023)

Farrowing pens with zero confinement are mostly equipped with partly slatted floor or solid floors. Due to the sows being able to move freely and due to that part of the floor being solid it is possible to provide more straw in these pen types. Many studies have investigated the effect of straw as nest building material on sow and piglet behaviour for farrowing pens with zero confinement, which are mostly equipped with (partly) solid floorings. A study by Westin et al. (2013) concluded that it is technically feasible to have an efficient

throughput of straw in farrowing pens with partly slatted floor and keep pen hygiene good as long as chop length and slath width are considered together. Using this principle, Westin et al. (2015) showed that allocation of large amount of straw (15-20 kg) pre-partum increased nesting activity. In addition, nesting behaviour was terminated earlier compared to when small amount of straw (0,5-1 kg chopped straw) was allocated. Also, piglet growth was increased and piglet skin abrasion and sole erosion was reduced with larger compared to smaller amount of straw (Westin et al., 2014). Providing a thick layer of straw (30 cm) also greatly reduced drop in body temperature immediate after birth (Pedersen et al. 2016), which increases

piglets chance of survival and growth (Pedersen et al 2011; 2015). Providing abundant nest materials as compared to a bucket of saw dust also increased nesting activity considerably and stimulated nursing hormones and behaviour of importance for piglet growth (Yun et al. 2013, 2014, 2015). Furthermore, Rosvold et al. (2019) showed that providing 2 kg long stemmed straw on the solid floor twice daily before and during farrowing, and to a lesser extent 4 kg peat twice daily, shortened the duration of farrowing and reduced percentage of still born.

Figure 4.2.1: Example on nest materials to sows with solid floor: chopped straw and long straw in a rack (©Aarhus University).

5 Conclusions

For crated sows during farrowing, type and allocation of material must be considered carefully, particularly with respect to floor type. Materials should either be presented quite frequently in front of the sows or be materials that can be attached to the side/front of the pen, e.g. rope and jute sacks. In pens with zero-confinement, many scientific studies (recently also reviewed by Monteiro et al., 2023), show that the allocation of large quantities of good quality nest material not only contributes to meeting the sow's need for nest building, but also contributes to increasing sow maternal care and improving piglet survival and growth.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank Marko Ruis for his valuable contributions to this short review.

6 References

- Algers, B., & Jensen, P. (1990). Thermal microclimate in winter farrowing nests of free-ranging domestic pigs. *Livestock Production Science*, 25(1-2), 177-181. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-6226\(90\)90051-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-6226(90)90051-7)
- Algers, B., & Uvnäs-Moberg, K. (2007). Maternal behavior in pigs. *Hormones and behavior*, 52(1), 78-85. <https://doi:10.1016/j.yhbeh.2007.03.022>
- Andersen, I. L., Berg, S., & Bøe, K. E. (2005). Crushing of piglets by the mother sow (Sus scrofa)—purely accidental or a poor mother?. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 93(3-4), 229-243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2004.11.015>
- Arey, D. S., Petchey, A. M., & Fowler, V. R. (1991). The preparturient behaviour of sows in enriched pens and the effect of pre-formed nests. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 31(1-2), 61-68. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591\(91\)90153-O](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591(91)90153-O)
- Bolhuis, J. E., Raats-Van den Boogaard, A. M. E., Hoofs, A. I. J., & Soede, N. M. (2018). Effects of loose housing and the provision of alternative nesting material on peri-partum sow behaviour and piglet survival. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 202, 28-33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2018.01.004>
- Cronin, G. M., Schirmer, B. N., McCallum, T. H., Smith, J. A., & Butler, K. L. (1993). The effects of providing sawdust to pre-parturient sows in farrowing crates on sow behaviour, the duration of parturition and the occurrence of intra-partum stillborn piglets. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 36(4), 301-315. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591\(93\)90128-C](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591(93)90128-C)
- Damm, B. I., Vestergaard, K. S., Schrøder-Petersen, D. L., & Ladewig, J. (2000). The effects of branches on prepartum nest building in gilts with access to straw. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 69(2), 113-124. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(00\)00122-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(00)00122-2)
- Damm, B. I., Lisborg, L., Vestergaard, K. S., & Vanicek, J. (2003a). Nest-building, behavioural disturbances and heart rate in farrowing sows kept in crates and Schmid pens. *Livestock Production Science*, 80(3), 175-187. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-6226\(02\)00186-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-6226(02)00186-0)
- Damm, B. I., Pedersen, L. J., Marchant-Forde, J. N., & Gilbert, C. L. (2003b). Does feed-back from a nest affect periparturient behaviour, heart rate and circulatory cortisol and oxytocin in gilts? *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 83(1), 55-76. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(03\)00111-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(03)00111-4)
- Jensen, P. (1986). Observations on the maternal behaviour of free-ranging domestic pigs. *Applied animal behaviour science*, 16(2), 131-142. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591\(86\)90105-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591(86)90105-X)
- Jensen, P. (1989). Nest site choice and nest building of free-ranging domestic pigs due to farrow. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 22(1), 13-21. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591\(89\)90076-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591(89)90076-2)
- Jensen, P. (1993). Nest building in domestic sows: the role of external stimuli. *Animal behaviour*, 45(2), 351-358. <https://doi.org/10.1006/anbe.1993.1040>
- Lawrence, A. B., Petherick, J. C., McLean, K. A., Deans, L. A., Chirnside, J., Gaughan, A., ... & Terlouw, E. M. C. (1994). The effect of environment on behaviour, plasma cortisol and prolactin in parturient sows. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 39(3-4), 313-330. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591\(94\)90165-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591(94)90165-1)
- Markland, L., Johnson, J. S., Richert, B. T., Erasmus, M. A., & Lay Jr, D. C. (2023). Investigating the effects of jute nesting material and enriched piglet mats on sow welfare and piglet survival. *Translational Animal Science*, 7(1), txad076. <https://doi.org/10.1093/tas/txad076>
- Mayer, J. J., Martin, F. D., & Brisbin Jr, I. L. (2002). Characteristics of wild pig farrowing nests and beds in the upper Coastal Plain of South Carolina. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 78(1), 1-17. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(02\)00114-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(02)00114-4)
- Monteiro, M. S., Muro, B. B., Carnevale, R. F., Poor, A. P., Araujo, K. M., Viana, C. H., ... & Leal, D. F. (2023). The beneficial effects of providing prepartum sows with nesting materials on farrowing traits, piglet

- performance and maternal behavior: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 259, 105795. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2022.105795>
- Oliviero, C., Heinonen, M., Valros, A., Hälli, O., & Peltoniemi, O. A. T. (2008). Effect of the environment on the physiology of the sow during late pregnancy, farrowing and early lactation. *Animal reproduction science*, 105(3-4), 365-377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anireprosci.2007.03.015>
- Pedersen, L. J., Damm, B. I., Marchant-Forde, J. N., & Jensen, K. H. (2003). Effects of feed-back from the nest on maternal responsiveness and postural changes in primiparous sows during the first 24 h after farrowing onset. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 83(2), 109-124. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(03\)00116-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(03)00116-3)
- Pedersen, L. J., Berg, P., Jørgensen, G., & Andersen, I. L. (2011). Neonatal piglet traits of importance for survival in crates and indoor pens. *Journal of Animal Science*, 89(4), 1207-1218. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2010-3248>
- Pedersen, L. J., Schild, S. L. A., & Malmkvist, J. (2015). The influence of the thermal environment and other early life events on growth rate of piglets during lactation. *Animal*, 9(9), 1529-1535. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731115001007>
- Pedersen, L. J., Larsen, M. L. V., & Malmkvist, J. (2016). The ability of different thermal aids to reduce hypothermia in neonatal piglets. *Journal of animal science*, 94(5), 2151-2159. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2015-0219>
- Pedersen, L. J., Patt, A., Ruis, M. A. W., Hoofs, A., Vermeer, H. M., & Kongsted, H. (2020). *Review on farrowing housing and management (version 1.0)*. EURCAW-Pigs review. <https://edepot.wur.nl/517902>
- Pedersen, L. J., Schubbert, A., & Vermeer, H. M. (2023). *Review on alternatives to farrowing crates (version 1.0)*. EURCAW-Pigs review. <https://edepot.wur.nl/588599> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7833648>
- Plush, K. J., McKenny, L. A., Nowland, T. L., & van Wettere, W. H. E. J. (2021). The effect of hessian and straw as nesting materials on sow behaviour and piglet survival and growth to weaning. *Animal*, 15(7), 100273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.animal.2021.100273>
- Rosvold, E. M., Newberry, R. C., Framstad, T., & Andersen, I. L. (2018). Nest-building behaviour and activity budgets of sows provided with different materials. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 200, 36-44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2017.12.003>
- Rosvold, E. M., & Andersen, I. L. (2019). Straw vs. peat as nest-building material–The impact on farrowing duration and piglet mortality in loose-housed sows. *Livestock Science*, 229, 203-209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2019.05.014>
- Thodberg, K., Jensen, K. H., Herskin, M. S., & Jørgensen, E. (1999). Influence of environmental stimuli on nest building and farrowing behaviour in domestic sows. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 63(2), 131-144. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(99\)00002-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(99)00002-7)
- Stolba, A., & Wood-Gush, D. G. M. (1989). The behaviour of pigs in a semi-natural environment. *Animal Science*, 48(2), 419-425. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003356100040411>
- Swan, K. M., Peltoniemi, O. A. T., Munsterhjelm, C., & Valros, A. (2018). Comparison of nest-building materials in farrowing crates. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 203, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2018.02.008>
- Vestergaard, K., & Hansen, L. L. (1984). Tethered versus loose sows: ethological observations and measures of productivity. I. Ethological observations during pregnancy and farrowing. In *Annales de Recherches Vétérinaires* (Vol. 15, No. 2, pp. 245-256). <https://hal.science/hal-00901502/document>
- Westin, R., Holmgren, N., Mattsson, B., & Algiers, B. (2013). Throughput capacity of large quantities of chopped straw in partly slatted farrowing pens for loose housed sows. *Acta Agriculturae Scandinavica, Section A–Animal Science*, 63(1), 18-27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09064702.2013.780633>

- Westin, R., Holmgren, N., Hultgren, J., & Algers, B. (2014). Large quantities of straw at farrowing prevents bruising and increases weight gain in piglets. *Preventive veterinary medicine*, 115(3-4), 181-190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2014.04.004>
- Westin, R., Hultgren, J., & Algers, B. (2015). Strategic use of straw increases nest building in loose housed farrowing sows. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 166, 63-70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2015.02.010>
- Yun, J., Swan, K. M., Vienola, K., Farmer, C., Oliviero, C., Peltoniemi, O., & Valros, A. (2013). Nest-building in sows: Effects of farrowing housing on hormonal modulation of maternal characteristics. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 148(1-2), 77-84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2013.07.010>
- Yun, J., Swan, K. M., Farmer, C., Oliviero, C., Peltoniemi, O., & Valros, A. (2014). Prepartum nest-building has an impact on postpartum nursing performance and maternal behaviour in early lactating sows. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 160, 31-37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2014.08.011>
- Yun, J., Swan, K. M., Oliviero, C., Peltoniemi, O., & Valros, A. (2015). Effects of prepartum housing environment on abnormal behaviour, the farrowing process, and interactions with circulating oxytocin in sows. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 162, 20-25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2014.11.006>

About EURCAW-Pigs

EURCAW-Pigs is the first European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare. It focuses on pig welfare and legislation, and covers the entire life cycle of pigs from birth to the end of life. EURCAW-Pigs' main objective is a harmonised compliance with EU legislation regarding welfare in EU Member States. This includes:

- for pig husbandry: Directives 98/58/EC and 2008/120/EC;
- for pig transport: Regulation (EC) No 1/2005;
- for slaughter and killing of pigs: Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009.

EURCAW-Pigs supports:

- inspectors of Competent Authorities (CA's);
- pig welfare policy workers;
- bodies supporting CA's with science, training, and communication.

Website and contact

EURCAW-Pigs' website www.eurcaw-pigs.eu offers relevant and actual information to support enforcement of pig welfare legislation.

Are you an inspector or pig welfare policy worker, or otherwise dealing with advice or support for official controls of pig welfare? Your question is our challenge! Please, send us an email with your question and details and we'll get you in touch with the right expert.

info.pigs@eurcaw.eu

www.eurcaw-pigs.eu

Services of EURCAW-Pigs

- **Legal aspects**
European pig welfare legislation that has to be complied with and enforced by EU Member States;
- **Welfare indicators**
Animal welfare indicators, including animal based, management based and resource based indicators, that can be used to verify compliance with the EU legislation on pigs;
- **Training**
Training activities and training materials for inspectors, including bringing forward knowledge about ambivalence in relation to change;
- **Good practices**
Good and best practice documents visualising the required outcomes of EU legislation;
- **Demonstrators**
Farms, transport companies and abattoirs demonstrating good practices of implementation of EU legislation.

Partners

EURCAW-Pigs receives its funding from DG SANTE of the European Commission, as well as the national governments of the three partners that form the Centre:

- Wageningen Livestock Research, The Netherlands
- Aarhus University, Denmark
- Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Germany